

Modelling 1D-2D Hydrodynamic SWMM Model to Mitigate Flooding and Priorities Flood Prone Area

Manish Kumar Sinha¹, Monika Sharma¹, Klaus Baier², Rafiq Azzam²

¹Department of Environmental & Water Resources Engineering, UTD, Chhattisgarh Swami Vivekanand Technical University Bhilai, India

²Department of Engineering Geology and Hydrogeology Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen, Germany

shubhamchandrakar386@gmail.com, baier@lih.rwth-aachen.de, azzam@lih.rwth-aachen.de

Urban Storm water modelling is considered to be a significant tool for flood mitigation and commonly used to mitigate urban storm flooding in developing countries such as India with large populations clustered in small areas with poor drainage conditions. During low-flooded years, people inhabit the surface areas and cause great harm when there is a greater flood. Urban floods are caused by increase of floodplains and unplanned drainage mechanisms. It leads to high-speed overland flow and water accumulation which presents an immense danger. Thus, it is important that the flood of rain-storms should be investigated and flood risk zoning should be done. This study covers a 1D-2D approach to model urban floods influenced by encroachment and connected with direct overland flow. A pilot study area taken as South-west part of Raipur City which is a capital city of Chhattisgarh State in India. 1D-2D model for pilot area has been developed in conjunction with 2D PCSWMM to simulate historical and designed events of rainfall for pre-development and post-development scenario. The purpose of this study is to estimate and compare storm water runoff from the catchment with those created before urbanization. Typically, the strategy used to compute the hydrologic response of the catchment. The results of the simulation process classify overflowing drainage nodes, flood maps. The flood risk maps identify areas that are low lying. The overflowing nodes show the need for improved drainage in the area to keep the storm water safe and to reduce flooding. Through observations, the model is validated and the error triggers analyzed. The effect of flood risks zoning indicates that higher recurrence precipitation produces larger areas of medium to extreme risk. This research would provide scientific support for the management of floods and disasters in the city of Raipur.

Keywords: 1D-2D PCSWMM model, Flood prone area, Flood inundation, SWMM model, Urban flood